

Acknowledgement

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Phytochemical Investigation of *Aesculus indica* Linn. and *Fragaria indica* Andr.

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AESCULUS indica Linn. (Hippocastanaceae)¹ is a large deciduous tree, used as folk medicine in various ailments² while *Fragaria indica* (Rosaceae)³ is a small perennial herb and said to be astringent and diuretic. Literature revealed that although some phytochemical work^{4,5} has been done on the leaves of *A. indica*, no such work has yet been reported on *F. indica*. We now report the results of systematic chemical examination of the stems of *A. indica* and the whole plant of *F. indica*.

The concentrated petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of the stems of *A. indica* upon chromatographic analysis over alumina yielded a compound in the petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (1 : 1) mixture eluate which, after repeated crystallization from acetone, afforded colourless plates, m.p. 65-67°, [$\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ 2945, 2825, 1450, 1370, 735 and 725 cm^{-1}].

It was identified as *n*-hentriacontane by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample.

The concentrated chloroform extract of the defatted stems of *A. indica* was subjected to systematic chromatographic analysis over silica gel. The benzene eluate furnished a solid, (M⁺, 414), m.p. 133-36°. It responded positive to Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol and was characterized as β -sitosterol by m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir with authentic sample.

Further elution of the column with benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) yielded a solid, C₁₅H₁₆O₉ (M⁺, 340), m.p. 205°(d); $\nu_{\max}$ 3320 (-OH), 1720, 1605, 820 cm^{-1} (coumarin). On hydrolysis with 4% H₂SO₄ it yielded an aglycone, C₉H₆O₄, m.p. 276° identical with aesculetin (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir, with authentic specimen)⁶ and D(+)-glucose (identified by paper chromatography with authentic sample) and was characterized as aesculin by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir and nmr spectra with authentic sample⁶.

Later fraction of benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluate gave another compound, crystallizable from methanol-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) mixture in pale yellow leaflets, m.p. 180-82°. It yielded an aglycone, identical in all respects with quercetin and L-rhamnose (identified by paper chromatography) on hydrolysis and was finally identified as quercetin through comparative studies (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic specimen of quercetin⁷.

Fragaria indica: The concentrated petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of the whole plant of *F. indica* was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (60-80°) furnished two compounds; one having m.p. 80-82° (M⁺, 438) and the other, m.p. 135-36° (M⁺, 414). These two compounds were identified as triacontanol and β -sitosterol, respectively by comparative studies (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

Fraction eluted with petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (1 : 1) yielded a triterpene, C₃₀H₅₀O, (M⁺, 426) [α]_D+27° (CHCl₃), m.p. 210-12°, $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3235; acetate, m.p. 214°, identified as lupeol by usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample⁸.

Further elution of the column with petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (1 : 2) yielded another triterpene, m.p. 258-60°, (M⁺, 426) characterized as friedlin through the preparation of its DNPH, m.p. 295-8° (d) and m.m.p. and co-ir with authentic specimen⁹.

Lastly, elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) also yielded a triterpene, m.p. 198-200°, (M⁺, 426); $\nu_{\max}$ 3425 cm^{-1} (broad, hydroxyl); acetate, m.p. 240-42°, characterized as β -amyirin through direct comparison (m.m.p., co-ir and co-tlc) with authentic sample¹⁰.

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Surface Waxes of Indian Mangrove Plants

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PLANT surfaces have been studied at regular intervals¹ since the early work of Aveguin in 1841 and Brongniart² in 1834. The last 15 years has seen considerable interest in plant surfaces and much work on the chemical composition has been recorded and reviewed³⁻⁵. One major stimulus for the study of plant wax constituents has been their possible use as chemotaxonomic criteria. The relative distribution of homologous series of wax components may act as a fingerprint for the individual species though Stransky and Streibl⁶ consider that the application of these distribution patterns for taxonomy purposes may be problematical. Tulloch⁷ summarised the taxonomic significance of leaf surface waxes and concluded that the waxes have been helpful in some plants, e.g. Crassulaceae, but not in other plants, e.g. Lignosae and Herbaceae. The plants examined in the present study grow in mangrove areas of the Sundarban region of West

Bengal, India, where they develop a peculiar physiology to cope with their unusual surroundings. Three of the plants, *Carapa moluccensis*, *Carapa obovata* (Meliaceae) and *Excoecaria agallocha* (Euphorbiaceae), belong to the order Geraniales and the other three, *Bruguiera gymnorhiza* and *Kandelia rheedii* (both Rhizophoraceae) and *Sonneratia apetala* (Sonneratiaceae), to the order Myrtiliflorae. It was hoped that a study of the surface waxes of these plants might be useful taxonomically, or might highlight the common features amongst the plants which could be related to their habitat, or suggest meaningful conclusions regarding the metabolic pathways under extreme extrinsic conditions.

Both *Carapa* species and the *Kandelia* species are believed to possess medicinal activity⁸. *Bruguiera gymnorhiza* contains cyanidin chloride⁹, *Sonneratia apetala* contains β -sitosterol, ursolic acid, gibberellin A₂, 3,3',4-trimethoxy-4'-hydroxydiphenic acid dilactone and 3,3'-dimethoxy-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenic acid dilactone^{10,11}. *Excoecaria agallocha* contains taraxeryl acetate, taraxerone, taraxerol, β -amyryn, β -amyrenyl acetate, β -amyrone, 3-epi- β -amyryn, epitaraxerol, friedelin, cycloartenol, β -sitosterol, behenic acid, exocarol and agacol¹²⁻¹⁴.

Experimental

Fresh leaves (6 g) of *Carapa obovata* were extracted with cold chloroform (15 ml) for 15 sec¹⁵. The chloroform was removed under reduced pressure yielding a residue (40 mg). The residue was refluxed with 10% methanolic potassium hydroxide (20 ml) for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) (30 ml $\times$ 3). The unsaponifiable matter (25 mg) was separated by tlc on silica gel using 10% diethyl ether in petroleum ether (40-60) as the eluent. The hydrocarbon fraction was extracted from the silica gel with chloroform. After the excess chloroform has been removed, the hydrocarbons were analysed directly by glc. The alcohol fraction (10 mg) was dissolved in pyridine (1 ml) and acetic anhydride (200 μ l) and the mixture allowed to stand overnight. Water (3 ml) was added to the reaction mixture and the resultant solution was extracted with diethyl ether. The acetates were then purified by tlc on silica gel before analysis by glc. The acidic fraction, which consisted of free acids and acids which were originally present as wax esters, was esterified and analysed by glc. By following the same procedure the other plants were extracted.

Gas liquid chromatography conditions: GLC analyses were performed on a Pye 104 dual Flame Ionisation detector instrument using 5 ft $\times$ $\frac{1}{8}$ inch columns. For methyl esters of fatty acids, alkyl acetates of alcohols and hydrocarbons, 1.5% OV17 on Gas Chrom Z (80-100 mesh) with temperature programming from 150 to 300°/min was used.

Results and Discussion

The hydrocarbons from the *Geraniales* plants each show some deviation from the most common